

Reusing precast concrete for a circular economy

Räsänen et al.

**Quality management best
practices in reuse of precast
concrete elements**

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Author(s)	Räsänen, A. (TAU), Lindman, N. (TAU), Matthews, B. (TU/e) & Lahdensivu, J. (TAU)
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Abstract

The ReCreate project researches reusing precast concrete elements, not originally designed for disassembly, through real-life deconstruction and reuse pilots in four European countries. A structured quality management process is crucial in ensuring that reclaimed precast concrete elements can be safely reused. It is also an essential prerequisite for upscaling and mainstreaming reuse. Throughout the deconstruction and reuse processes, the properties of reclaimed elements must be preserved, and any damage that may have occurred must be accurately detected and addressed.

The current report outlines best practices for quality management in the reuse of precast concrete elements, based on insights from ReCreate's pilot projects. It emphasises a structured approach, beginning with a preliminary assessment of reusability and followed by material property evaluation through existing data or structural testing. The selection of testing methods should align with reliability requirements, considering both cost-effectiveness and accuracy. Elements are categorised based on damage during deconstruction, with structural expertise guiding the assessment. Careful analysis of test results ensures informed design decisions, with additional studies conducted when necessary. Comprehensive documentation of quality assurance measures is crucial for demonstrating reusability to stakeholders and regulatory authorities.

List of abbreviations

Cl ⁻	Chlorides
CM	Cover meter
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
COV	Coefficient of variation
DC	Diaelectric constant
DT	Destructive testing
EM	Electromagnetic
GPR	Ground-penetrating radar
HCS	Hollow-core slab(s)
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KL	Knowledge level(s)
LDT	Locally destructive testing
NDT	Non-destructive testing
RH	Rebound hammer
RN	Rebound number
SEM	Standard error of the mean
TVOC	Total volatile organic compounds
UPV	Ultrasonic pulse velocity

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1. Introduction

One of the focal objectives of the ReCreate project has been to determine necessary quality management measures in reuse of concrete elements. The quality of reclaimed concrete elements depends on the original production quality (material and structural properties) as well as their present condition, which may have deteriorated from the original condition as a result of use and deconstruction. The quality management process has been explored through real-life deconstruction and reuse pilot projects conducted in Finland, Sweden, the Netherlands, and Germany.

Prior to the current report, which provides a best practice proposal, the quality management process has been discussed in Räsänen et al. (2024a; 2024b). In Räsänen et al. (2024a), the properties and condition of the elements deconstructed in ReCreate's pilots were discussed, whereas in Räsänen et al. (2024b), a general overview of the essential stages of the quality management process was provided (Figure 1). Quality management is closely linked to other phases of a reuse project, particularly deconstruction (see Vullings et al. 2024) and redesign and reassembly. More information about these phases can be found in ReCreate's other deliverables.

Like any other building materials, reclaimed concrete elements must meet general construction requirements, essential technical specifications, and regulatory procedures. Specific requirements may have been established at the national level. In general, buildings must withstand estimated loads and fulfil characteristics related to their intended use. Typically, these characteristics include strength and stability, fire safety, service life, health factors, user safety, acoustics, and energy efficiency.

Quality management is an essential part of the reuse process. Its purpose is to ensure that the quality of reclaimed elements remains at least at the same level as that of equivalent new products when it comes to meeting the aforementioned requirements. The process contributes to structural safety, where a greater amount of data provides greater reliability. However, gathering data can lead to high costs if numerous measures are required, the timing of the measures is incorrect, or if expensive test methods are used. By optimising quality management measures, sufficient reliability levels and a fluent, cost-efficient reuse process can be achieved.

The current deliverable examines in detail the best practical measures and their timing in a reuse project. The measures recommended in the report have been gathered from the experiences gained from ReCreate's pilots, so their effectiveness has been validated in the field.

The structure of this report is as follows. Chapter 2 discusses the key quality management measures and their timing, which been identified with the help of ReCreate's pilots. Chapter 3 focuses on the planning of structural investigation, which plays a central role in ensuring successful outcomes for the quality management process. Chapter 4 covers the main test methods for structural investigation. Chapter 5 examines the key methods for interpreting

investigation results. Chapter 6 provides a brief overview of how the quality management process is documented. Chapter 7 discusses briefly the experiences from ReCreate’s pilots and the quality management process in general. Finally, Chapter 8 concludes the report by summarising the main findings from the previous sections.

Figure 1. Action modules of quality management process (Räsänen et al. 2024b).

2. Essential quality management measures

The quality management best practice for reclaimed concrete elements proposed in this report consists of several phases. The necessary measures in these phases vary depending on whether the objective is to determine structural properties or to verify the condition of the elements. Figure 2 supplements Figure 1 by illustrating the temporal progression of typical stages of a reuse process, and the recommended quality management measures (sampling, testing, and inspections) and their timing.

Figure 2. Timing of sampling, testing, and visual inspections in a reuse process.

Sampling

Sampling is typically conducted to determine material properties from the elements for analysis. For a reliable analysis, the sampling requires high reliability. In some cases, sampling may also be necessary to assess the condition of elements, especially if signs of deterioration can be visually observed. It is recommended to conduct sampling before deconstruction for the following reasons:

- **Poor sampling results** - i.e. poor values, large variance, or poor consistency - may limit reuse possibilities or lead to the rejection of elements. Early testing allows the deconstruction plan to account for both reusable and unsuitable elements.
- **Presence of harmful substances**, requiring special treatment, can be identified before deconstruction and addressed in deconstruction and/or refurbishment plans.
- **Environmental exposure conditions**, which have impacted the elements in the donor building, can be evaluated during the investigations. Deterioration of the structural condition might be due to stresses the elements have been exposed to during use.

- **Sampling can be performed year-round** in a warm environment and even while the building is in use. In the Nordic countries, though, outdoor sampling is impractical in the winter due to water-related issues with freezing, when using sampling methods that need water.
- Sampling before deconstruction **eases the deconstruction process**, eliminating the need to schedule sampling alongside other work.
- Storage space may be limited, making **access to reclaimed elements** challenging while they are stockpiled.
- **Design** of the new building **can commence immediately** after obtaining the investigation results, accelerating the reuse process.

Visual inspections

Damage can occur to elements during deconstruction due to various mechanical and environmental stresses, potentially affecting their quality (Räsänen et al., 2024b). To streamline the deconstruction and reuse process, it is essential to follow the condition of the elements during deconstruction. Rejecting clearly damaged elements that do not need to be preserved helps to avoid unnecessary work.

During deconstruction, only general visual inspections are recommended to identify severely damaged elements. Conducting precise assessments of minor defects may be impractical under deconstruction site conditions. Detailed inspections require time and expertise, and performing them during deconstruction could slow down the overall schedule.

After deconstruction - typically during storage and before refurbishment - a more thorough inspection of the elements should be conducted. This is a crucial stage for assessing their condition and determining the need for further tests. Sufficient time should be allocated for this inspection to ensure a reliable evaluation.

Detailed inspections can typically reveal even small defects that require further study or repairs before reuse. These assessments allow for the final rejection of unsuitable elements before refurbishment and so help to avoid unnecessary work and costs.

Further tests

In addition to tests performed on material samples, further tests may be necessary if deficiencies are identified after interpreting the sampling results and/or visual inspections. Typically, further tests involve additional samples or the application of new test methods (see Chapter 4). The initial sampling results may be unrepresentative, and thus, additional samples or other test methods may be required to improve representativeness and reliability. Moreover, potential systematic defects in elements may lead to consistent weakening of resistance. This need not mean the elements must be disqualified, but it can be taken into account in design values based on the tested influence of the defect.

Efforts should be made to optimise further testing to reduce costs. Additional testing must be well justified, especially for expensive methods, such as full-scale tests or destructive core sampling.

Final inspection and on-site acceptance inspection

Once the necessary testing and inspections have been carried out on the elements, refurbishment measures, required by the new application, can be performed. After the refurbishment, the elements must undergo a final inspection, just like newly manufactured concrete elements. The purpose of this inspection is to ensure the quality of the refurbishment before the elements are sent for reuse. A similar inspection must also be carried out on-site at the new location, where the elements and their quality are approved before installation, as in the case of new products.

3. Structural investigation plan

3.1. Procedure

The actual condition, remaining service life, and probable repair needs of elements intended for reuse can be assessed through a systematic investigation. The aim is to determine the existence, degree, extent, mechanism and reason of degradation, e.g. corrosion of reinforcement, or cracking of concrete (Lahdensivu et al., 2019). In the case of load-bearing concrete structures, concrete compressive strength must be determined, along with reinforcement details, which are necessary for structural, service life, and fire safety calculations. Testing methodologies for deriving design values, partial safety factors, and, therefore, overall reliability of reused elements, are determined by the information available about the original design. Based on the extent of this information, deconstruction projects can typically be categorised into four Knowledge Levels (KLs):

1. **Knowledge Level 1 (KL1):** No information is available regarding the concrete quality, reinforcement properties, or the manufacturer of the elements.
2. **Knowledge Level 2 (KL2):** No information regarding the material qualities is available, but the manufacturer is known.
3. **Knowledge Level 3 (KL3):** Some specifications describing the concrete and reinforcement properties of the elements exist, but no further information about the manufacturer or quality control applied during production is available.
4. **Knowledge Level 4 (KL4):** Detailed archives of specifications describing the used concrete quality and reinforcement steel design are available, and both the manufacturer and its quality control system are well-documented.

The first two knowledge levels (KL1 and KL2) describe situations where no design specifications are available on the donor building. In these cases, extensive non-destructive testing (NDT) and destructive testing (DT) is required. For KL3 and KL4, partial or complete archives of original documents are accessible, and the specified properties only need to be verified through selective testing, reducing the workload. This knowledge-based framework can be leveraged to determine the necessary structural investigation procedure for reclaimed precast concrete elements in all kinds of cases (Figure 3).

Depending on the KL, the systematic investigation procedure consists of (Lahdensivu et al., 2019; fib Bulletin 111, 2024):

- gathering and analysing relevant information from available documents and visual inspections of the structures,
- carrying out investigations with necessary sampling,
- laboratory tests of samples, and
- analysis of results, and reporting.

Figure 3. A simple decision flow chart for testing based on the quality of the information. Adapted from Räsänen et al. (2024b), KLs added.

Figure 4 presents the main stages of a structural investigation from the perspective of the investigator, with the client's perspective indicated in dashed lines.

Figure 4. Recommended flowchart for condition investigations. Adapted from Lahdensivu et al. (2019).

3. 2. Defining the scope of structural investigation

Investigation content

Planning the scope of a structural investigation is one of the most important phases of the structural investigation process (Lahdensivu et al., 2019). The aim is to identify the correct and relevant measures in accordance with the investigation objectives, using a sufficiently large number of samples and sufficiently precise methods.

The content of the investigation is always shaped by the characteristics of the donor building (such as structural types, materials, exposure conditions, and already visible damage) and the specific goals set based on the KL. By assessing these factors, it is possible to form an understanding of what types of properties, damage or functional deficiencies may exist in the elements and what their significance is. First, potential issues in the building's structural types and exposure conditions are identified, and based on these, the investigation content is determined (measurable and observable parameters, methods used, and necessary extent of sampling).

Investigating existing structures always involves uncertainty, as data is collected through sampling, and the structure's properties and condition can vary across different areas. The condition investigation should aim to collect parallel data from as many sources as possible (design documents, visual inspection of structures and damage, complementary research methods, sampling, and laboratory analysis) (Lahdensivu et al., 2019). Furthermore, the amount of available documentation, and thus uncertainty, can vary significantly between projects. Documentation of existing structures is commonly lost or inaccessible. The fewer design and material specifications available, the more sampling and testing needs to be performed. The use of parallel methods facilitates the evaluation of results and improves the reliability of conclusions.

Investigations should proceed in an incremental stepwise manner, beginning with simple and inexpensive methods (Lahdensivu et al., 2019). Only after this should more expensive methods be used to address the remaining information gaps. Data collection should generally be performed by structural and element type, and within each distinct structural or element type, by type of damage, using sufficiently extensive sampling. Test regions are defined in Section 5 of EN 13791 (2019) as groups of concrete elements produced under the same controlled conditions and of the same material characteristics. Hence, material testing should be performed in accordance with EN 13791 (2019) guidelines.

The most common and significant types of damage prevalent in concrete structures include reinforcement corrosion and cracking or deformation caused by various environmental or exposure factors, e.g. mechanical stresses from use. In addition, previous repairs and the presence of substances hazardous to human health or the environment must be considered.

In the case of multiple buildings, conclusions should never be based solely on a single investigated building as each building is a different test region (Lahdensivu et al., 2019). Even neighbouring buildings may differ significantly in terms of exposure conditions and susceptibility to damage, due to factors such as varying construction conditions, work techniques, weather during construction, available labour, and raw materials (cement, aggregates, and various admixtures). Therefore, different buildings should be investigated individually as separate test regions.

Structures on the donor building often consist of different types of elements, which may also have various surface types and materials. Different materials, manufacturing and construction methods, and structural properties cause variations in the progression of deterioration and damage phenomena. In such cases, results obtained from samples taken from one element type cannot be generalised to all elements. Therefore, multiple elements from a given test region should be sampled to ensure broad coverage of these factors.

The number of samples defined in the investigation plan should not be treated as a goal. Instead, sampling should be adapted as the investigation progresses so that, for example, samples may not be needed from areas that are already visibly extensively damaged. On the other hand, to detect damage that is not yet visually observable, denser sampling is necessary. The recommended number of samples for different test methods is presented in Chapter 4.

Preliminary assessment

In the preliminary assessment phase, relevant information is collected to determine whether an investigation is necessary and to define its scope (Lahdensivu et al., 2019). The broader and more thorough the preliminary assessment is, the more precisely the content of the structural investigation can be defined.

It is recommended that planning the scope of the investigation begins with a review of all available design documents, such as structural and element drawings. These documents help to form a clearer understanding of the building's structural types, static behaviour, and potential functional deficiencies. Studying the design documents enables assessing the elements' properties and vulnerability to damage, which is influenced by factors such as the types of structures, structural details, materials and surface types, and the level of exposure (e.g. moisture stress from outside and inside, freeze-thaw stress, drying potential, thermal movements, etc.). Without documents, the same factors should be assessed by examining elements and structural solutions in the field. In addition to observations, the lack of documentation (KL 1 and KL 2) must be considered when selecting test methods and determining the number of samples.

Even on KL3 and KL4, the structures may not have been implemented exactly according to the design. Therefore, information found in the design documents should initially be treated as indicative, and its accuracy should be evaluated in conjunction with investigations in the field.

A visual inspection of the donor building further refines the need for investigation and helps to identify practical considerations related to conducting the investigation. During the visual inspection, an effort should be made to assess the donor building's exposure conditions and how the stresses are distributed across various elements to appropriately target the investigation. Additionally, the inspection aims to evaluate visible damage, its extent, and its significance. Only far advanced damage can typically be identified through visual inspection alone.

Investigation plan

After the visual inspection and review of any available documentation, the investigator should discuss with the client what is expected from the investigation relative to the knowledge level and define the objectives together (Lahdensivu et al., 2019). The client's expectations must not excessively limit the scope of the investigation. To ensure the accuracy and reliability of any conclusions drawn from the investigation, it is of utmost importance that all significant material properties, damage mechanisms, and functional deficiencies are considered. Based on these aspects and their significance, decisions are made regarding which parameters to observe and measure, and what tests are required. Taking this into account, along with the available resources, it is then determined which measurements and methods will be used and what is the necessary number of samples. The result of this work is a field investigation and sampling plan, as well as a plan for the required laboratory tests and their extent.

Usually, even a broad preliminary assessment does not provide sufficient information, and field investigation must be carried out to gather more detailed observations and measurement data (Lahdensivu et al., 2019). The investigation work plan defines which properties and damage mechanisms should be studied, what parameters are observed, and what research methods are used. The investigation work plan specifies the structures, structural components, and damage mechanisms to be studied, along with the methods to be used, detailed to a sufficient degree. It also outlines how the structures are divided into separately examined test regions.

Resources available for the investigation must be allocated as wisely as possible - primarily to the investigation and verification of the most critical issues (Lahdensivu et al., 2019). For example, assessing the condition of a structure that appears to be in good shape may require thorough investigative procedures since early-stage damage may not be visible on the surface. In contrast, damage in a deteriorated structure may already be identifiable through visual inspection alone, and extensive investigations may no longer be necessary.

At the planning stage of the investigation, it is often not possible to determine the full final scope of the investigation (Lahdensivu et al., 2019). As the work progresses, there may be matters that require broader or more in-depth investigation than originally anticipated, or matters that need not be investigated separately or with the intended level of detail.

4. Test methods

Many different test methods are available for determining properties of concrete elements. Some methods are simple, while others are more complex, potentially causing more damage and costs. Additionally, the reliability of the tests varies depending on the method used. The testing methods used should always be selected to suit each specific situation, based on the project's criteria. The criteria may include, e.g. the type of element, required level of reliability, requirements of the new building, or the test methods available.

Ideally, the methods should be selected to maximise the amount of knowledge gained while minimising costs and time. By combining test methods, reliability can often be improved by complementing each method's shortcomings to create a more reliable aggregated method.

More detailed information on the test methods is presented in the sections below, including references to possible parallel methods. The methods discussed in this report are based on the most commonly available methods as well as those used in ReCreate.

4.1. Geometry

Dimensions of elements should always be determined as part of the investigation process. These measurements are especially important for design – such as calculating load-bearing capacity or defining the dimensions for a new building. While dimensions can often be obtained from design documents, they may differ from the actual built elements. In some cases, original plans may be missing entirely, requiring measurements to be taken for each element type individually.

Additionally, damage may occur during dismantling, which could result in elements being or needing to be shortened. Therefore, measurements should ideally be taken after deconstruction but well in advance of the design phase for the new project. This ensures designers are aware of any dimensional discrepancies and have accurate quantities of elements in different lengths.

Measurements can be easily taken using simple methods, such as tape or laser measures, or with more complex tools, such as laser scanners, all of which offer relatively small measurement errors. These methods are quick and straightforward to use – though careful execution remains important to ensure accuracy.

4.2. Compressive strength

Determination of compressive strength is an essential part of reusing concrete elements, especially load-bearing elements. Engineers should select the most suitable methods to evaluate the strength, acknowledging possible uncertainties and variations. Compressive strength can be determined using several different methods, with the most reliable being the direct DT of core samples drilled from the elements. However, core sampling involves

many uncertainties, including the drilling location and the size of the core sample (Haavisto et al., 2020). Additionally, drilling core samples damages the structure, and conducting the test is relatively slow and expensive. Furthermore, to determine the characteristic value, a sufficiently representative number of samples is needed due to potential variation in strength within the building and the elements. The European standard EN 13791 (2019) limits the minimum number of core samples to 8 for normal-sized test regions, but recent research indicates that the sufficient number for determining the characteristic strength may be as high as 12–15 to achieve adequate reliability (Räsänen et al., 2025).

For fast, low-cost, and non-invasive testing, non-destructive methods have been developed, such as the rebound hammer (RH), ultrasonic pulse velocity (UPV), and SonReb (RH and UPV combined). However, these methods involve greater uncertainties because compressive strength is assessed indirectly based on the surface hardness or sound waves propagating through the concrete. The properties of the concrete on the surface can differ from the rest of the concrete, especially in terms of hardness, if carbonation has progressed significantly in the element. In EN 13791 (2019), the carbonation is limited in RH testing to a depth of 5 mm (for more detail on carbonation, see Section 4.5). Additionally, mix characteristics and member characteristics (e.g. geometry and coating) can significantly influence the results of RH (Bungey et al., 2018). UPV also involves uncertainties due to various factors, which can lead to more than 20 % uncertainty in strength assessment (Bungey et al., 2018).

The SonReb method, which integrates both RH and UPV test results taken at the same location, is based on the premise that the limitations of each method are mitigated when applied in combination, enhancing the accuracy of compressive strength estimations. E.g. relative humidity inversely affects the two techniques – as humidity increases, the rebound number (RN) decreases, while pulse velocity increases (Breysse, 2012). Furthermore, UPV yields a deeper penetration into the concrete specimen, capturing internal structural properties, whereas RH characterises the surface hardness, providing a more holistic understanding of the concrete member's condition when used in combination.

Extensive databases have been compiled in ReCreate on each NDT method for estimating the concrete compressive strength – RH, UPV, and SonReb. A total of 16,531 unique NDT-compression strength sets were collected from 115 publications, comprising 10,428 RH tests, 6,103 UPV tests, and 3,299 SonReb tests. Of these, 3,042 RH tests, 1,328 UPV tests, and 544 SonReb tests were conducted on in-situ structures, with the remainder performed on laboratory specimens (Matthews et al., 2025a).

Error! Reference source not found. illustrates the global relationships between NDT measurements (after removing outliers) and compressive strength normalised to a reference cylinder of 300×150 mm for consistency with EN 1992-1-1 (2023). Given the comprehensiveness of the databases, it is assumed they reflect the true global variability and sensitivity of each NDT method. Both RH and UPV show significant uncertainty in their ability to explain the compressive strength, demonstrating clear non-linear relationships on the global scale. Hence, as concrete strength increases, the applicability of these testing methods becomes more limited, especially that of UPV.

Figure 5. Global distributions of each NDT method from the compiled database. RH (left); UPV (middle); SonReb (right) (Matthews et al., 2025b).

Rebound hammer has the most potential for high-strength ranges, as new devices which store larger nominal kinetic energies can provide more reliable results, as shown by Chen et al. (2023). To manage the large variability observed in Figure 3, machine learning models have been developed as a more robust alternative to conventional empirical modelling techniques, such as the simple linear regression recommended by EN 13791 (2019) (Matthews et al., 2025a).

These methods should be used in parallel or combination with core samples, allowing for a more representative sampling with relatively minimal labour. EN 13791 (2019) gives guidelines for combining these methods.

Table 1 summarises various test methods for evaluating the compressive strength of existing concrete elements.

Table 1. Test methods for compressive strength evaluation of existing concrete elements.

Test method	Core test	Rebound hammer	UPV	Pull-out test
Standards	EN 12504-1 (2021) EN 13791 (2019)	EN 12504-2 (2021) EN 13791 (2019)	EN 12504-4 (2021) EN 13791 (2019)	EN 12504-3 (2005)
Representativity	moderate	local	moderate	local
Reliability	high	moderate	moderate	weak
Workload	high	moderate	moderate	high
Minimum number of elements	8 ¹⁾³⁾ For high reliability: 12-15 ²⁾	EN 13791 (2019) ³⁾	EN 13791 (2019) ³⁾	- ⁴⁾

¹⁾ EN 13791 (2019) based on ≥ 75 mm diameter core.

²⁾ Räsänen et al. (2025) based on ≥ 75 mm diameter core.

³⁾ Depends on the scope of the investigation and parallel methods.

⁴⁾ No mention, depends on the variability of compressive strength.

4. 3. Reinforcement yield strength

The yield strength of reinforcement is a critical design parameter in designing concrete structures. If the yield strength of reinforcement steel in reclaimed concrete elements is unknown, it is recommended to determine it in order to assess the structural integrity. In practice, testing should be conducted on extracted samples obtained through destructive methods according to EN ISO 6892-1 (2019) and EN ISO 15630-1 (2019). The primary sample sets should focus on the diameters that contribute the most to the structural resistance.

Even discarded elements can be used for testing purposes – as long as it is ensured that the reinforcement in the test samples is the same type as that found in the elements intended for reuse. This ensures the test results accurately represent the reclaimed components.

In cases where the number of reusable elements is limited, a minimum of six rebar specimens should be collected. Secondary sample sets from the rebars that do not contribute the most to the structural resistance should also be tested if varying diameters are present to verify whether a consistent steel grade was used across all bars. A smaller number of samples may be justified for simple validation purposes. If inconsistent grades are determined through the sample parameters, the minimum number of tests of six rebars must be satisfied to obtain the stable statistical distribution required in Chapter 5.

4. 4. Cover depth and reinforcement diameter

Concrete cover depth to the reinforcement is crucial for structural design, service life assessment, and fire resistance evaluation. Typically, non-destructive methods (e.g., cover meters and ground-penetrating radars (GPRs)) are used for estimating the cover depth, offering variable reliability. However, the most reliable local measurement can be achieved by exposing the bars through locally destructive testing (LDT) methods – but is more labour-intensive than NDTs.

Cover meters are based on electromagnetic (EM) fields, allowing quick and cost-effective measurements. These devices can also estimate the diameter of the reinforcement bars and spacing between adjacent bars, but past research has revealed significant uncertainties in this method (Selek, 2015).

GPR is an NDT technology that transmits EM waves through solid materials to detect subsurface objects or defects (Tosti & Ferrante, 2020). The speed and amplitude of EM waves vary depending on the parent material properties, particularly the dielectric constant (DC), which influences wave penetration. Factors such as moisture conditions, relative humidity, concrete quality, density, and reinforcement type impact the in-situ DC and wave propagation (Lai et al., 2018).

The effective cover depth of an element is a critical property for structural design. To determine a reliable value of the effective depth and the accompanying uncertainty (necessary for the steel reinforcement partial safety factor), two databases were compiled from cover meter (CM) and GPR tests published in the literature. The CM database is organised into two datasets: rebar diameter estimations (835 results) and concrete cover depth measurements (1,844 results). These components are combined in the GPR database (784 results), yielding a total of 3,463 test results from 26 published studies: 10 for CM diameter measurements, 15 for CM cover measurements, and 15 for GPR. Of the CM tests, 1,965 were performed on in-situ elements and 714 on laboratory specimens. For GPR, 574 tests were in-situ, and 210 were on laboratory specimens. The full bibliographic lists and open-source databases are available in Matthews et al. (2025c), with documentation detailing all assumptions, nomenclature, and abbreviations applied.

Both NDT methods present distinct advantages and challenges in mapping reinforcement. No scientific consensus exists on a reliable method for quantifying rebar diameters from GPR radargrams. Consequently, the CM is generally preferred for estimating the rebar diameter at small cover depths, particularly for the first and second (if perpendicular) reinforcement layers. Modern GPR devices, which offer greater range and advanced functionalities like 3D modelling (Agred, 2019), provide more comprehensive mapping capabilities for deeper layers.

The accuracy of the CM diminishes once the cover depth exceeds 60 mm, depending on the probe type used. In such cases, GPR may be more appropriate for the initial detection of deeper layers. Other physical characteristics that can influence reliability include rough surfaces, small edge distances from the device path, limited surface area for the device, and difficulties around corners or geometric discontinuities. To improve accuracy, the scanned path should align with the rebar, with measurements recorded in the clear spacing between intersecting perpendicular bars.

For deeper members, accurately assessing rebar diameter, cover depth, and spacing of inner layers becomes challenging. In these situations, selective LDT – such as spot-checking – may be necessary in conjunction with 3D mapping from GPR devices to verify measurements. Cross-validated 3D visualisations by combining GPR and CM data may help overcome limitations in densely reinforced areas or with lap splicing (Wiwatrojanagul et al., 2018; Zhou et al., 2018; Donkervoort, 2024). Ambiguous regions in the maps should be further examined using a combination of NDT and LDT methods.

For the cover meter, the British BS 1881: Part 204 (1988) and the more recent BS EN 12504-5 (2023) provide guidance on testing procedures, applications, and limitations. For GPR, BS EN 302 066-1 (2019) outlines its use for detecting objects in concrete, while ACI 228.2R-13 (2013) provides details on the applications and limitations of GPR technologies.

Donkervoort (2024) investigated potential improvements in accuracy when combining NDT with selective LDTs on reclaimed precast elements. Several independent parties mapped the reinforcement in various precast elements without prior knowledge of the design or specifications. In phase 1, using NDT alone, the research found that rebar diameter measurements were grossly unreliable, although concrete cover depth measurements

were adequate. After conducting LDT at strategic locations and updating the NDT approach based on posterior knowledge, the number of incorrect rebar diameter measurements decreased from 80% to 22.9% for reclaimed façade elements and from 80% to 0% for an in-situ inclined column.

Regardless of the method, each element and reinforcement type must be assessed separately, as variations can occur within reinforcement types and elements. According to Räsänen & Lahdensivu (2025), sufficient representative sampling for cover depth measurements requires 150 random measurements from each reinforcement and element type.

Table 2 summarises various test methods for evaluating the cover depth and diameter of reinforcement.

Table 2. Test methods for cover depth measurements.

Test method	Cover meter		Measuring from samples		Measuring in the field from openings	
	Cover depth	Diameter	Cover depth	Diameter	Cover depth	Diameter
Standards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Representativity	local	local	local	local	local	local
Reliability	good	low	high	high	high	high
Workload	moderate	low	high	high	high	high
Minimum number of elements	150 ^{1) 3)} for each reinforcement type	1 ^{2) 3)} element	150 ¹⁾	1 ^{2) 3)} element	150 ¹⁾	1 ^{2) 3)} element

¹⁾ Räsänen & Lahdensivu (2025)

²⁾ Sufficient only if the same diameter has been used in each element.

³⁾ Each element type must be considered separately.

4. 5. Corrosion risk of reinforcement

Carbonation depth

When carbon dioxide (CO₂) from the air penetrates concrete, it reduces concrete's alkalinity (Chang & Chen, 2006). This process is known as carbonation. The carbonation process slows as it progresses from the surface deeper into the concrete. The penetration rate of CO₂ is influenced by the pore structure of the concrete surface, which in turn depends on several factors such as the type of cement, water-cement ratio, degree of hydration, compaction, and mix proportions (Neville, 2011). Additionally, external factors like relative

humidity temperature, CO₂ concentration, and stress distribution affect the rate of the reaction (Liu et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2023).

When relative humidity exceeds 75%, carbon dioxide penetration slows down significantly, whereas below 40%, the reaction does not occur at all (Liu et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2023). Higher temperatures, increased CO₂ concentration, and greater stress levels accelerate carbonation (Peng et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2018). Due to these various influencing factors – as well as cracks and spalls – the carbonation process does not progress uniformly across an element.

If the alkalinity of concrete drops too low, the risk of reinforcement corrosion increases. Corrosion can start already at pH value of 11 (Tuutti, 1982). However, even if the alkalinity is low, corrosion process is not activated until enough moisture and oxygen is present.

The carbonation depth can be easily measured by applying pH-indicator solutions to freshly broken concrete surfaces. The indicators reveal the pH threshold specific to the indicator used. Two common indicators for carbonation depth measurements are phenolphthalein and thymolphthalein. The current standards do not specify the number of samples required for determining carbonation depth from existing structures, but based on research performed in ReCreate, a sufficient number of samples for carbonation depth measurement is between 12 and 14 (Räsänen & Lahdensivu, 2025).

For a more precise assessment, the carbonation depth can be determined using thin-section methods on a concrete sample. However, this method is more labour-intensive, causing higher costs compared to sprayed indicators.

Table 3 summarises test methods used for carbonation depth measurement.

Table 3. Test methods for carbonation depth measurements.

Test method	pH-indicator	Thin section
Standards	EN 14630 (2007)	-
Representativity	local	local
Reliability	good	high
Workload	moderate	very high
Minimum number of samples/tests	12-14 ¹⁾	12-14 ¹⁾

¹⁾ Räsänen & Lahdensivu (2025)

Chloride content

Chlorides (Cl⁻) in concrete can initiate reinforcement corrosion, even in alkaline concrete, if the structure is exposed to wind-driven rain or otherwise humid environment. Chlorides

may already be present in concrete due to additives, or contaminated aggregate or contaminated water used during the manufacturing process. The allowed chloride content in concrete is limited to 0.10–1.0 % of the cement mass, as specified in EN 206:2014 (2021). However, for existing concrete elements, the amount of cement may be unknown. Thus, the cement mass needs to be assumed in order to compare the chloride content to the concrete mass. This assumption can lead to significant loss of accuracy in the determination of chloride content in concrete if the assumed cement mass is not correct. In general, the accuracy of the methods for determining chloride content in cement is relatively good, usually being within ± 0.2 % by mass of cement (Bungey et al. 2018).

Chlorides can also ingress into concrete elements from external sources such as de-icing salts and seawater, usually by diffusion, but also through cracks. Since chloride contamination significantly affects the durability of concrete, it is essential to determine chloride concentrations – especially when there is suspicion that the concentration exceeds permitted limits. It is also worth noting that a change in environmental conditions between dry or fully saturated concrete can accelerate corrosion if sufficient chloride concentration is present at the steel interface.

The chloride content in existing concrete elements can be measured using a powder sample, according to EN 14629 (2007); see Table 4. The powder sample can be collected from a drilled core or directly by drilling powder from the element. Additionally, the risk of corrosion can be assessed using various methods, such as measuring the potential of the reinforcement (Bungey et al., 2018). This helps evaluate the presence of corrosion. These methods can be useful in identifying potential hotspots to help improve sampling efficiency and decision-making.

The probable chloride content in elements can be determined with a small number of samples, which is enough to indicate the possibility of high chloride concentration. If chlorides have been absorbed from external sources, sampling should be aimed at areas where they are suspected to have penetrated the concrete elements. In such cases, localised sampling may be sufficient to assess the risk. However, if the goal is to obtain a representative chloride content across the building and all elements, a larger number of samples is recommended. BRE (1986) recommends sampling 10% of the building elements.

Table 4. Test methods for chloride content of concrete.

Test method	Drilling powder	Slices of core sample
Standards	EN 14629 (2007)	EN 14629 (2007)
Representativity	local	local
Reliability	moderate	high
Workload	low	very high
Minimum number of samples/tests	3 for local analysis ¹⁾ 10% of the elements ¹⁾	3 for local analysis ¹⁾ 10% of the elements ¹⁾

¹⁾ BRE (1986)

Corrosion deterioration

The potential risk of reinforcement corrosion in concrete elements can be evaluated by determining the cover depth of reinforcement, carbonation depth, and chloride content. However, corrosion conditions can be assessed visually by inspecting the elements for deterioration caused by advanced corrosion. Additionally, by exposing reinforcement through chiselling or by examining samples, it is possible to determine whether the corrosion is active and how far it has progressed locally. Methods related to corrosion risk assessment can be used for evaluating the likelihood of corrosion at a specific location, which can help to target the sampling. In cases of carbonation-induced corrosion, the risk can be assessed by focusing on areas with the lowest concrete cover, where carbonation is most likely to reach the reinforcement. However, factors influencing the rate of carbonation must also be taken into consideration during the evaluation.

If active corrosion is confirmed, various methods can be used for directly measuring the corrosion rate to evaluate the remaining service life. However, the current report focuses on assessing the corrosion risk rather than determining the rate of corrosion. This is because the measured rate of corrosion is for a specific environment, and the environment typically changes in a reuse process. Therefore, the measured rate of corrosion in the original environment may not represent the situation in the new application. Moreover, active corrosion is only relevant in high humidity environments, e.g. outdoors, where the corrosion can advance. Reusing elements with active corrosion is not recommended in such environments unless repair measures are taken, as the time until damage can be short.

Table 5 summarises the most used methods for evaluating corrosion conditions.

4. 6. Freeze-thaw resistance of concrete

Concrete structures in XF exposure classes must be resistant to freezing and thawing (EN 206:2014, 2021), which should also be considered when reusing concrete elements. For concrete to achieve sufficient frost resistance, it must contain protective pores with appropriate spacing. Protective pores are defined as having diameters between 0.01 mm and 0.3 mm (EN 206:2014, 2021). Guidelines for spacing can vary at the national level. For example, according to Finland's national guidelines, an adequate spacing factor ranges between 0.23 and 0.30 mm, depending on the water-to-cement ratio and the XF exposure class (Tikkanen et al., 2023).

Beyond the exposure conditions in a building, deterioration from freezing and thawing can also occur during storage, especially in Nordic climates, if the concrete is not protected from direct moisture contact. Additionally, high-strength concrete has better resistance to freeze-thaw deterioration without protective pores (Pigeon & Pleau, 1995). Despite this, it is generally recommended to protect the elements during storage to prevent potential freeze-thaw deterioration.

Table 5. Test methods for corrosion of reinforcement caused by chlorides or carbonation of concrete (Lahdensivu & Tikkanen 2025).

Test method	Detectable corrosion grade	Representativeness	Reliability	Workload	Needs sampling
Visual inspection	very advanced corrosion, already breaking the concrete surface	wide	moderate	low	no
Cover depth of reinforcement	¹⁾	wide	moderate	moderate	no
Chloride content	¹⁾	local	moderate	moderate	yes
Carbonation depth	¹⁾	local	moderate	moderate	yes
Visual inspection of samples	early phase corrosion	local	high	high	yes
Permeability of concrete	potential of chloride content water penetrating to concrete pore structure	local	high	very high	yes
Exposing reinforcement	very early-phase corrosion	local	very high	high	yes

¹⁾ The amount of reinforcement in a corrosive state can be estimated by comparing the cover depth to the carbonation depth and chloride content of the concrete, relative to the reinforcement depth. The actual corrosion rate must always be ensured by exposing reinforcement.

Table 6. Test methods for freeze-thaw resistance of concrete.

Test method	Protective pore test	Petrographic examination (spacing factor)	Freeze-thaw test
Standards	SFS 4475 (1988)	ASTM C856/C856M-20 (2020) ASTM C457/C457M – 24 (2024) NT BUILD 381 (1991)	SFS 5447 (1988)
Representativity	local	local	local
Reliability	high	high	very high
Workload	moderate	high	high
Minimum number of samples	3 per element type	3 per element type	3 per element type

Concrete porosity can be tested by measuring air content or using petrographic analysis on a polished sample surface (Pigeon & Pleau, 1995). The petrographic analysis also provides information on the local distribution of protective pores. Since porosity varies within a concrete element, a sufficient number of samples is needed to obtain a representative assessment. Concrete freeze-thaw durability can also be tested using an accelerated freeze-thaw test. The test is harsher than typical environmental conditions, but provides insight into the concrete's durability under normal exposure conditions.

According to Finnish condition investigation guidelines for concrete facades (Lahdensivu et al., 2019), the minimum number of samples should be at least 3 per element type. When assessing concrete facades (as these are the most susceptible elements to external environments), it is recommended to take one sample from the area most exposed to rain and one from the least exposed area to ensure a comprehensive evaluation.

Table 6 summarises test methods for evaluating the freeze-thaw resistance of existing concrete elements.

4.7. Full-scale testing

In cases where structural resistance cannot be verified through local sampling or ND methods, full-scale tests are required to confirm the structural resistance of elements for new applications. According to the Norwegian standard NS 3682 (2022), the shear resistance of reclaimed hollow-core slabs should always be tested through load testing. Additionally, full-scale testing may be necessary if the elements exhibit damage affecting their structural capacity, and when the impact of this damage needs to be assessed.

Load testing can be used to determine the resistance of a specific failure mechanism (Figure 6). When designing such tests, it is important to consider both the type of element and its potential failure mechanisms. Because load testing is relatively expensive and labour-intensive, it should only be used when indispensable. If required, these tests must be carefully planned to ensure they are effective and representative.

Figure 6. Shear strength test of HCS. Photos by TAU/Eetu Lehmusvaara.

Based on an assessment conducted as part of the Finnish pilot, an adequate number of samples for verifying the shear resistance of hollow-core slabs (HCS) may range from three to six (Figure 7), depending on the variability in the observed shear resistance. For 4% coefficient of variation (COV) even 2 samples should be enough, while for 15% COV, at least 6 is needed for the same accuracy. Specimens P20-4x are HCS 200mm in height with four prestressing strands, while P20-7x are HCS 200mm in height with seven strands. Each element type with a different design should be considered as its own population. Additionally, elements in a good structural condition and elements with deficiencies must always be considered separately.

Figure 7. Standard error of the mean as a function of number of samples for the shear resistance of HCS in the FI pilot.

4. 8. Harmful substances

Harmful substances are one of the most significant factors affecting the potential for reuse. Reclaimed concrete elements must not contain concentrations of harmful substances that exceed current regulations. Many harmful substances are related to raw materials used during manufacturing, meaning they may bind to the concrete matrix and no longer pose a direct risk to users. However, some harmful substances, e.g. asbestos, impact those working with the elements, such as deconstruction and refurbishment workers, and thus protective measures for workers should be determined based on the concentration levels of harmful substances. Therefore, the potential presence of harmful substances should be investigated for two reasons:

- exposure risk to the deconstruction workers and refurbishment workers, and
- risk to the users of the new building.

In addition to harmful substances that may be present in concrete elements from the manufacturing process, other harmful substances can be absorbed into concrete during

its use – e.g. from surrounding materials, such as seams and paint. The absorbed substances may differ from those used during production, so the investigation can be divided into two categories based on the source of the harmful substances:

- substances bound during manufacturing, and
- substances absorbed during use.

Various test methods exist for investigating harmful substances, many of which are mentioned in national guidelines. Typically, methods rely on material sampling and laboratory analysis. The need to sample for the presence of a given substance is often assessed based on when the substance has been prohibited from being used in construction material production.

During the pilots, it was noticed that currently EU-wide standards for identifying harmful substances in existing structures are insufficient¹. Regulations and limit values for harmful substances in existing buildings have been established at the national level, as will be presented in Chapter 5.3. However, at the time of writing, no other systematic guidelines for buildings' hazardous substance investigation are known, except for the Finnish RT 103501 (2022). Detailed methods and concentration levels of the harmful substances examined in ReCreate's real-life pilots are available in Räsänen et al. (2024a).

4. 9. Cracking and damage

Cracking

Cracks and damage can develop on concrete structures due to various factors. In reclaimed concrete elements, cracks may have developed before installation in the donor building, during use in the donor building, or during the reuse process. Small cracks are generally acceptable since they mainly affect appearance, but larger cracks can impact structural safety and durability and must be considered. Eurocode 2 provides guideline values for acceptable cracking widths for durability, which also apply to reclaimed concrete elements (EN 1992-1-1, 2023). National guidelines may set specific limits on cracking.

Cracks can be assessed visually and measured. Assessment should be conducted at different stages throughout a reuse process to identify potential causes quickly. If significant cracking appears only in few individual elements, those elements can be discarded immediately to avoid further tests. However, if damage or cracking occurs systematically in multiple elements, assessment is necessary to evaluate its impact on

¹ The use of substances that pose risks to human health and/or the environment in new building materials is regulated by EU chemical legislation, specifically the REACH Regulation EC 1907/2006 (2006) and the POP Regulation EU 2019/1021 (2019). At the EU level, comparative concentrations of chemical substances based on health criteria are guided by EU-LCI reference values (Lowest Concentration of Interest). Additionally, the World Health Organization (WHO, 2010) has established its own guideline values for several chemical compounds. These regulations and guidelines apply when hazardous chemicals are manufactured and used, but they alone do not provide sufficient support for evaluating the presence and risks of such chemicals in reclaimed concrete elements.

structural integrity and reusability of the elements. This can lead to further experimental testing.

In prestressed concrete elements, especially HCS, even minor cracks can significantly affect the structural capacity if the cracking occurs in critical areas. The Dutch guideline Kiwa 73/07 (2017) for new HCS outlines various crack types, their impact, and the necessary inspections (Figure 8). Critical cracking types for structural capacity have been highlighted. These must always be carefully analysed with extra attention to ensure structural capacity, and it is rather recommended to use non-cracked elements. If the cracks are in the end of the element, it may be possible to cut off the damaged part and reuse the rest of element, i.e. local cracking or damage does not always mean the element cannot be used at all.

Figure 8. HCS cracking types and their significance on structural capacity, modified from Kiwa 73/07 (2017). Critical crack types for structural capacity are highlighted.

Deterioration

Structural elements may deteriorate over time if they have been exposed to conditions that promote degradation. Typically, advanced deterioration appears as visible cracking, spalling, and potentially staining from rust seepage, which can be detected through a visual inspection. However, cracking can also occur internally and not yet be visible. In such cases, early signs of deterioration can be assessed using various methods, including hammering, visual inspection of samples, tensile strength tests, or petrographic analysis (Table 7). It is worth noting that other useful methods for studying deterioration exist that are not mentioned in this report, including ultrasonic methods, thermography, dynamic, radiography, holography, acoustic, soundness, chemical, etc., that are more expensive and impractical (Bungey et al., 2018).

Damage caused by deterioration can affect the suitability of elements for reuse by shortening their lifespan. Aggressive external substances, e.g. chlorides, sulphates and acids, can penetrate concrete more quickly through cracks and existing damage, increasing the rate of deterioration. However, repairing the damage can significantly extend

the elements' lifespan. To ensure elements remain usable in a new application, it is essential to determine the root cause of any deterioration. If the degradation mechanism persists, repairs alone will not provide a long-lasting solution.

Table 7. Test methods for deteriorated concrete (Lahdensivu et al., 2019).

Test method	Detectable degree of deterioration	Representativeness	Reliability	Workload	Needs sampling
Visual inspection	very far advanced deterioration	wide	low	low	no
Heavy hammering	far advanced deterioration	rather wide	moderate	moderate	no
Visual inspection of samples	far advanced deterioration	local	moderate	high	yes
Tensile strength test	early phase weathering ¹⁾	local	high	high	yes
Micro-structure from thin section	very early phase weathering, reactive aggregates and ASR ¹⁾	local	very high	very high	yes

¹⁾ ASR detected in a microstructure study must be ensured with a tensile strength test and vice versa. Two parallel samples are always needed.

5. Interpretation of results

Accurate interpretation of test results is critical in reuse projects, as it has a significant impact on both reliability and costs. Misinterpreting data can lead to underestimated design values, which, in the worst case, may result in inadequate structural durability. On the other hand, incorrect interpretation can also lead to unnecessary further tests, potentially driving up costs substantially. Therefore, with sufficient expertise and well-interpreted results, it is possible to ensure both reliability and cost-effectiveness.

5.1. Test results

When interpreting results, the first step is to consider the intended purpose of the findings. In reuse projects, research results are typically needed for one of two scenarios:

- **Determining a characteristic value for an unknown property**
This applies when the value of a property is unknown, requiring a tested design value to be established.
- **Verifying a known property**
In this case, the property is already known (e.g. from original design documents) but needs verification through testing.

Determining a characteristic value for an unknown property

When determining a design value, the reliability of results is crucial. The derived value must have sufficient safety to ensure that even untested structural elements have a minimal probability of exceeding it. For example, in assessing the compressive strength of existing concrete structures according to standard EN 13791 (2019), the characteristic value must be set so that at least 95% of the elements exceed the specified value. The reliability of the testing method plays a key role here.

Test results can be interpreted using simple mathematical methods that evaluate the distribution of data obtained from the sample population according to EN 13791 (2019), see Eq. 1. Often, for simplification, it is assumed that the properties follow a normal distribution. This allows the characteristic value to be estimated based on a point in the distribution where a specific percentage of observations falls below, i.e. a quantile.

For a normally distributed random variable, the mean yield strength, standard deviation, and the 5th percentile characteristic value can be approximated by the sample values as:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \quad (2)$$

$$X_{ck} = \bar{x} \pm t_{\alpha, n-1} * \sigma \sqrt{1 + \frac{1}{n}} \quad (3)$$

Where (X_{ck}) is the characteristic value, x_i is an individual result (\bar{x}) is the sample mean, ($t_{\alpha, n-1}$) is the t-distribution value corresponding to a specific percentile in the cumulative distribution function based on degrees of freedom, (σ) is the sample standard deviation, and (n) is the number of samples. A t-distribution, used for small number of samples when the sampling distribution has uncertainties for estimating population, has heavier tails compared to a standard normal distribution.

When determining a characteristic value, it is crucial to consider the directionality of the distribution. This affects whether the final part of Eq. 1 is subtracted or added to the mean. For example, when assessing compressive strength or reinforcement cover depth, the lower tail of the distribution is examined, while for carbonation depth, the upper tail is more interesting. Determining the characteristic value for cover depth of reinforcement and carbonation depth is especially useful when defining the design values for service life and fire resistance. The characteristic value allows the assignment of a design value based on a specific probability, which is similar to the design of new concrete elements.

It is also essential to recognise that the formula assumes a perfect symmetric normal distribution. However, concrete properties do not always follow an assumed distribution, which can cause the calculated characteristic value to differ from the actual one (Räsänen et al., 2025). In EN 1992-1-1 (2023), the compressive strength of concrete and reinforcement yield strength are assumed to follow log-normal distribution. Assuming the random variable x_i follows a log-normal distribution, the log-normal parameters (mean and standard deviation) can be related to the underlying normal distribution parameters and Eq. 3 can be used in logarithmic form to better reflect the distribution, shifting its centre towards lower values (Eq. 6):

$$LN(\bar{x}) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n LN(x_i) \quad (4)$$

$$LN(\sigma) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (LN(x_i) - \bar{x})^2} \quad (5)$$

$$X_{ck} = \exp(LN(\bar{x}) \pm t_{\alpha, n-1} * LN(\sigma) \sqrt{1 + \frac{1}{n}}) \quad (6)$$

Verifying a known property

In contrast, verifying a known property does not involve determining an exact numerical value but rather confirming that the results reliably exceed the known value. In such cases, it is sufficient to check that the test results are significantly higher than the established value. Here, the reliability of the testing method is less critical than in defining a design value – so long as the results clearly surpass the known threshold.

Chapter 9 of standard EN 13791 (2019) outlines verification methods for compressive strength assessments, including indirect testing approaches and their combined use. However, no standardised method exists for verifying other material properties. To address this, the same mathematical approach used to determine characteristic values (Eq. 3 and 6) can be applied. Here, the calculated characteristic property value must be greater than the known value. In this case, lower reliability can be accepted. Additionally, smaller numbers of samples can be reliable enough, but representativeness of the sampling results must be assessed and deemed as acceptable.

Verifying a known specification is typically necessary for load testing, where the number of samples is relatively small. The assessment involves comparing the average test result from load testing to the calculated value. Importantly, individual test specimens must not fall below the calculated value. Additionally, all test specimens must be completely undamaged to ensure representative results.

For analysing test results, the Norwegian reclaimed HCS standard NS 3682 (2022) provides an evaluation method requiring the following conditions to be met:

- $F_{\text{MEAN}} \geq 1.25 \times$ estimated characteristic capacity, when $n < 6$;
- $F_{\text{MEAN}} \geq 1.10 \times$ estimated characteristic capacity, when $n \geq 6$.

Where F_{MEAN} represents the mean test result.

Great caution must be taken when analysing load test results to ensure the evaluation is sufficiently reliable. Proper analysis requires mathematical skills and a deep understanding of structural design to interpret the findings accurately.

Adjustment of partial safety factors for materials (EN 1992-1-1)

According to Annex A of EN 1992-1-1 (2023), the partial safety factor for concrete compressive strength, reinforcement tensile strength, or shear capacity can be adjusted. This is especially applicable in cases where material properties are verified through testing, such as core sampling for concrete, or tensile tests for reinforcement. Adjusting the safety factor in this way allows designers to account for deviations in material quality during structural design. The method is presented in the annex A of the EN 1992-1-1 (2023).

Sufficiency of the number of samples

The minimum number of samples specified in testing methods discussed in Chapter 4 is typically adequate, but larger samples may be needed for the sampling results to be representative. Sample representativeness should be evaluated alongside the test results,

allowing for additional samples to be collected or different testing methods to be used, if necessary.

Determining a sufficient number of samples is challenging, as the sampled population may not fully represent the entire set of elements. However, sample sufficiency can be assessed based on the variation within the results – greater variability suggests a larger number of samples is needed, while lower variability indicates that a smaller number of samples may be sufficient. Analysing the variation observed within and between elements can help identify changes in material quality.

There is no fixed threshold for determining whether variability is acceptable, so assessments must be made on a case-by-case basis. In practice, coefficient of variation (COV) can be used as a tool for assessing variability, see Eq. 7 and 8 (Haldar & Mahadevan, 2000). COV measures the dispersion of a probability distribution or frequency distribution, and presents the ratio of standard deviation and mean value. No recommended COV values can be given, as it depends on the property, safety level, test method, deviation and mean value. However, a high COV indicates poor material quality and the need for additional samples.

$$COV = \frac{\sigma}{\bar{x}} \quad (7)$$

$$COV (LN) = \sqrt{LN\left(1 + \left(\frac{\sigma}{\bar{x}}\right)^2\right)} \quad (8)$$

Where (σ) is the sample standard deviation, and (\bar{x}) is the sample mean.

Another approach is to evaluate the number of samples based on the standard error of the mean (SEM) using Eq. 9 and 10 (Devore, 2015). SEM estimates how far the sample mean deviates from the population mean. The SEM value can then be compared to the sample mean to assess the reliability of the sample in representing a given property. As in COV, no recommended SEM values can be given for the same reasons.

$$SEM = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}} \quad (9)$$

$$SEM (LN) = \frac{LN(\sigma)}{\sqrt{n}} \quad (10)$$

Distribution of results

Analysing the distribution of results can provide valuable insights into the sufficiency and representativeness of a sample. If the sample distribution follows the assumed distribution, the sample is very likely representative, given that the number of samples is sufficient. However, if the distribution deviates from the assumed distribution, it may indicate poor quality or the presence of non-representative values in the sample, such as different concrete grades or reinforcement types. For example, EN 1992-1-1 (2023) assumes a log-normal distribution for both the concrete compressive strength and steel yield strength.

Therefore, each element and reinforcement type should be treated as separate populations to ensure accurate evaluation.

If the distribution shows two distinct peaks, the sample likely includes two different populations, meaning that there are two distinct test regions. In such cases, the results should be treated separately to avoid incorrect assumptions about uniformity.

Corrosion risk

To assess the extent and risk of corrosion, it is necessary to analyse results related to carbonation, cover depth of reinforcement, and possible chloride contamination. The extent of corrosion is particularly important when determining the suitability of elements for reuse and selecting appropriate repair measures.

The extent of corrosion due to carbonation can be evaluated by comparing the distributions of carbonation depth and cover depth of reinforcement from collected samples. The comparison reveals the percentage of observations where the reinforcement cover has undergone carbonation, indicating potential active corrosion (see Figure 9).

Figure 9. Comparison of carbonation and cover depth of reinforcement distributions.

When assessing corrosion, it is essential to consider whether active corrosion was possible during the first use of the elements. If exposure conditions were not conducive to corrosion, comparing carbonation and cover thickness distributions may not yield meaningful insights. Conversely, if the elements are to be reused in an environment with more exposure to corrosive conditions, this risk must be factored into both reuse assessment and storage decisions. Additionally, potential repair needs and associated costs should be considered when evaluating feasibility. Since the proportion of carbonated concrete cover varies across each element type, its determination should be performed individually.

The progression of carbonation can be assessed using a simple square-root model, which is based on the measured carbonation depth during the element’s first use (Eq. 11).

$$X_{carb} = k\sqrt{t} \quad (11)$$

Where x_{carb} is the carbonation depth (in mm), k is the carbonation rate (or carbonation coefficient in mm/ $\sqrt{\text{year}}$), and t is the time (in years).

However, the rate of carbonation is not exactly the same in a new setting, as it also depends on external factors – such as environmental conditions – as well as the properties of the concrete itself, as discussed in Chapter 4. Therefore, the evaluation of carbonation progression in the new application must be based on these specific conditions.

That said, a design value for corrosion caused by carbonation can still be calculated using data from the first application. According to Eq. 3 and 6, characteristic values can be determined for both the carbonation depth and the concrete cover thickness of the reinforcement. By subtracting the characteristic carbonation depth from the characteristic cover depth, one obtains the *non-carbonated* portion of the cover for a given probability level. Using Eq. 11, the remaining time until active corrosion can then be calculated – provided the carbonation rate for the new application is known. It is also worth to note that in exposure class XC1, where the corrosion rate is approximately zero, carbonation does not limit the service life of the structure, as corrosion is not possible.

The steps for determining the residual service life of reclaimed elements are:

- Determine characteristic value for carbonation depth,
- Determine characteristic value for cover depth of reinforcement,
- Determine non-carbonated cover depth by subtracting characteristic carbonation depth from characteristic cover depth,
- Evaluate carbonation rate (or carbonation coefficient) for new application,
- Determine time from Eq. 11,
- Consider corrosion possibility in new application.

The risk of chloride-induced corrosion depends on the source of the chlorides. If the chlorides originate from the concrete production process, their concentration should be compared to the recommended limit values 0.10–1.0 % of the cement mass, as specified in EN 206:2014 (2021). If the chlorides come from external sources, their concentration can be examined at different depths and compared to the distribution of cover depth of reinforcement. Based on these concentration levels, the necessary measures can be determined to prevent active corrosion in the reuse environment.

5. 2. Visual inspections

Visual inspections of elements should be conducted throughout the entire reuse process, as previously mentioned. While the requirements for inspections vary across different phases, the overall objective remains the same: identifying elements that are not suitable for reuse. This section examines the requirements and interpretation of inspections based on Chapter 2, outlining key factors to consider at each stage.

Visual inspection during deconstruction

The primary goal of visual inspection during deconstruction is to identify clearly defective elements to avoid unnecessary efforts in carefully removing unusable components. Since deconstruction is typically fast-paced and tightly scheduled, additional work steps that may slow down the process are often considered as undesirable.

For this reason, it is recommended to perform inspections at a general level, avoiding detailed analysis or measurements during deconstruction. Additionally, smaller defects may be difficult to detect under deconstruction site conditions. Thus, the site inspection can be carried out by a designated person familiar with rejection criteria, and a more thorough evaluation should be conducted later by a qualified specialist. If needed, a specialist can also be consulted on-site during deconstruction.

The types of defects that lead to rejection before or during deconstruction are notable and serious damage and depend on the element type. In general, rejection is based on damage occurring in critical structural areas, such as connection points or high-stress zones. If there is uncertainty regarding rejection criteria, consultation with a specialist is always advised.

Damaged elements from ReCreate's pilot projects that were deemed unsuitable for reuse, both before and after deconstruction, have been illustrated in Vullings et al. (2024) and Räsänen et al. (2024b).

Thorough inspection after deconstruction

Once structural elements have been successfully deconstructed, they must be subjected to a careful visual inspection. As previously mentioned, small cracks can go unnoticed on site, but they may significantly impact structural capacity. For example, longitudinal cracks inside HCS cores can drastically affect their load-bearing capacity.

Following deconstruction, all potential defects must be identified and their effects assessed. This evaluation can be performed based on experience, calculations, or experimental testing. The key requirement is that the impact of every defect is accounted for, regardless of whether the damage is located in a critical structural area.

For this reason, the inspection must be carried out by a qualified professional who understands structural behaviour and the potential consequences of even minor defects. Additionally, the effect of damage on the installation process, such as lifting work safety, must be considered.

Since damage assessments are case-specific, providing general guidelines is challenging. The Kiwa 73/07 (2017) guideline outlines necessary measures for different types of cracks for new products, but the guideline is suitable for reclaimed elements, too. As a general principle, it is always recommended to reuse undamaged elements whenever possible.

5. 3. Harmful substances

If high concentrations of harmful substances are detected, their solubility and potential risks must be evaluated case-by-case. Recognising that not all substances remain harmful in fully cured concrete structures is very important.

In Finland, the main problematic substances identified in the context of the pilot were Total Volatile Organic Compounds (TVOC) and 2-Ethylhexanol, found in the screed of HCS. However, after removing the screed, no concentrations exceeding regulatory limits were detected in the HCS themselves.

In Sweden, the most significant challenge was Chromium VI, which was found in relatively high concentrations. However, the risk associated with Chromium VI applies mainly to fresh concrete during the manufacturing process. Once concrete hardens, contact with it is considered as safe, as the Chromium VI concentration decreases over time as it binds chemically within the concrete matrix. Chromium VI is not water-soluble, further reducing its potential exposure risk.

In both the Netherlands and Germany, the primary harmful materials affecting reclaimed facade elements were asbestos-containing materials that had been in contact with the elements. Asbestos becomes dangerous when it turns into airborne dust, which is why it must always be removed through specialised asbestos abatement procedures before any other deconstruction or demolition work takes place.

Harmful substances can vary greatly depending on the specific case, as seen in the pilots. It is recommended to apply threshold values according to current regulations only for substances that pose health risks during deconstruction, refurbishment or use the elements. For substances that are not harmful after the manufacturing phase, investigation is unnecessary. The harmful level and threshold values should be assessed individually for each substance, ensuring that regulations are appropriately applied based on actual risks. Since there are no international guidelines for investigating harmful substances, it is essential to follow national guidelines in reuse projects. National regulation and limit values used in the ReCreate pilots were derived from:

- Finland: Sosiaali- ja terveysministeriön asetus asunnon ja muun oleskelutilan terveydellisistä olosuhteista sekä ulkopuolisten asiantuntijoiden pätevyysvaatimuksista 545/2015, (2015),
Sosiaali- ja terveysministeriön asetus haitallisiksi tunnetuista pitoisuuksista 654/2020, (2020),
Valtioneuvoston asetus rakennustyön turvallisuudesta 205/2009, (2009),
- Sweden: Bygg-IS-1 (ALS, 2020),
- Netherlands: Asbestverwijderingsbesluit (2005),
- Germany: TRGS 519 (2014),
TRGS 521 (2008).

6. Documentation

Documentation is a critical part of quality assurance in reuse projects, and every phase of the reuse process must be appropriately documented (Räsänen et al., 2024b). The purpose of these documents is both to communicate results to clients and authorities, and to store essential information for future reference. To ensure data is easily accessible and usable, documents should be prepared as clearly and consistently as possible.

The most important documents regarding element reusability relate to material properties, testing procedures, bearing capacity, and inspections. These records also serve as proof of reusability, which may be required by regulatory authorities. The content of each document depends on the specific procedure, but reports should typically address or include the following key aspects:

Structural investigation

- Summary presenting the key findings
- Table of contents
- Identification and general information about the project
- Objectives and scope of the investigation
- Actions performed and methods used
- Observations and measurement results
- Conclusions regarding the material properties and condition of the elements
- Factors compromising safety and health
- Further studies required
- Appendices, e.g. images

Deconstruction

- Identified deficiencies and their description (with photos)
- Reasons and quantity of rejected elements, and their location in the donor building.

Visual inspection after deconstruction

- Identified deficiencies and their description (with photos)
- Reasons and quantity of rejected elements
- Elements designated for further tests, including reason

Further tests

- Objectives and scope
- Actions performed and methods used
- Observations and measurement results
- Conclusions based on the results
- Appendices, e.g. images

Refurbishment

- Summary of required and planned repair actions
- Repaired elements and their quantity
- Summary of completed repairs and modifications

Final inspection

- Possible deficiencies identified with reason and action required, e.g. repaired, rejected or accepted

Documentation to prove reusability (for authorities)

- Description of the elements, the donor building, and the new building
- Brief overview of the quality assurance process and its phases
- Summary of inspections and tests
 - Methods and results of structural investigation
 - Methods and results of further studies
 - Acceptance criteria for element inspections
- Repair actions performed
- Design values of elements
 - Characteristic material properties
 - Expected service life in new application

7. Discussion

Quality assurance measures carried out in the ReCreate project varied somewhat across different pilots (Räsänen et al., 2024a). The best practices presented here are based on the necessary actions taken at each pilot. In particular, damage and deficiencies in structural elements required significant interventions. These defects were discovered at different stages of the pilots, leading to immediate responses each time, which resulted in multiple actions being taken.

To streamline the process, inspections and expertise should be focused on cleaned elements during storage. This allows for a thorough inspection to be conducted all at once. On the other hand, utilising expertise at the deconstruction site before and during deconstruction helps minimise work during storage. If non-reusable elements can be discarded during deconstruction, unnecessary storage and handling can be reduced. Therefore, deconstruction workers should review the deconstruction plan together with structural engineers, including criteria for rejecting elements.

The analysis of material properties was conducted in a similar manner across all pilots. The scope of testing varied by country, but the experiments were based on the same European standards and methodologies (Chapter 4). However, the investigation and identification of harmful substances varied significantly between countries due to national requirements. At the time of writing, there are no unified European-level guidelines for assessing harmful substances in existing structures. Despite this, identifying harmful substances was deemed as crucial in proving elements' suitability for reuse, particularly in the Finnish and Swedish pilots, where extensive assessments were conducted. The need for load testing also varied between countries, largely depending on the quality of the elements. In the Finnish pilot, a considerable number of defects were found, requiring further studies and tests, including load testing, to assess their impact.

Overall, the quality assurance measures presented in Figure 2 and Räsänen et al. (2024b) were especially useful in validating the reusability of elements. These measures also benefited designers by helping them anticipate potential deficiencies and necessary modifications during refurbishment. Well-documented processes provided evidence of reusability to authorities and other stakeholders involved in the reuse process. Therefore, the procedures outlined in this report are recommended for future projects entailing concrete element reuse.

8. Conclusions

This report presented the best practices for the quality management process in the reuse of precast concrete elements. The proposed practices are based on the experiences and actions taken in ReCreate's real-life pilots.

The quality management process begins with a preliminary assessment, where the reusability of elements is evaluated based on the available information about the building. After the initial assessment, the material properties of the building should be determined either from existing data or through structural testing. While original specifications may provide sufficient information, verifying the condition of elements through a separate structural investigation is recommended. The extent of this evaluation depends on the condition of the elements and the objectives of the study.

Various methods exist for assessing material properties, and their suitability depends on the required level of reliability. If little information is available about the elements, using more reliable methods for determining properties is advised. Less reliable methods can still be helpful for verifying specific characteristics, as they are typically non-destructive and, hence, faster and more cost-effective. However, the selection of testing methods should always be planned on a case-by-case basis.

To ensure a smoother reuse process, elements should be categorised as acceptable or rejected based on potential damage during deconstruction. If significant damage occurs during deconstruction, the affected elements should be discarded immediately before transport and storage. What 'significant damage' is, varies depending on the type of element, so it should be defined by a structural engineer before deconstruction. If necessary, consultation with a structural engineer should also take place during deconstruction. Alternatively, sorting can be done during storage after the elements have been cleaned, allowing for the identification of even minor defects. At this stage, strong expertise in structural engineering and damage assessment is crucial. A final inspection should also be conducted after refurbishment to verify the defects have been remedied as planned.

The results of tests and inspections must be analysed carefully. It is important to determine whether the number of samples is sufficient and whether the results are representative. This has a significant impact on the design phase, where potential deficiencies must be taken into account. Additional studies may be required if the results indicate uncertainty.

To demonstrate reusability, all quality assurance measures must be properly documented. These documents are valuable not only to project participants but also to regulatory authorities overseeing the reuse.

In the future, developing EU-wide harmonised product standards for reclaimed concrete elements could significantly enhance the efficiency and prevalence of reuse in the EU, ensuring that quality management methods would not differ substantially between projects.

References

205/2009. (2009). *Valtioneuvoston asetus rakennustyön turvallisuudesta*. <https://www.finlex.fi/fi/lainsaadanto/saaduskokoelma/2009/205>

545/2015. (2015). *Sosiaali- ja terveysministeriön asetus asunnon ja muun oleskelutilan terveydellisistä olosuhteista sekä ulkopuolisten asiantuntijoiden pätevyysvaatimuksista*. <https://www.finlex.fi/fi/lainsaadanto/saaduskokoelma/2015/545>

654/2020. (2020). *Sosiaali- ja terveysministeriön asetus haitallisiksi tunnetuista pitoisuuksista*. <https://www.finlex.fi/fi/lainsaadanto/saaduskokoelma/2020/654>

ACI Committee 228. (2013). *Report on Non-destructive Test Methods for Evaluation of Concrete in Structures*. ACI 228.2R-13. American Concrete Institute. Farmington Hills, MI, USA.

Agred, K. (2019). *Localisation automatique des aciers et caractérisation de la teneur en eau du béton armé par radar double-offset à grand rendement [Automatic localization of steels and characterization of the water content of reinforced concrete by double-offset radar at high yield]*. PhD Thesis. University of Toulouse, Toulouse, France. [in French].

ALS. (2020). *Bygg-IS-1 Grundämnen (II) i byggnadsmaterial, 7M HNO3 uppslutning*. https://www.alsglobal.se/paket/milj-1/avfall-och-byggnadsmaterial_36/grundmnen_5/bygg-is-1-grund-mnen-ii-i-byggnadsmaterial-7m-hno3-uppslutning_17450

Asbestverwijderingsbesluit BWBR0019316 (2005). <https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0019316/2024-08-01>.

ASTM C457/C457M-24. (2024). *Standard Test Method for Microscopical Determination of Parameters of the Air-Void System in Hardened Concrete*. ASTM International.

ASTM C856/C856M-20. (2020). *Standard Practice for Petrographic Examination of Hardened Concrete*. ASTM International.

BRE. (1986). *Determination of cement and chloride contents of hardened concrete*. Information paper QP21/86. Building Research Establishment, Garston.

Breysse, D. (2012). *Non-destructive evaluation of concrete strength: An historical review and a new perspective by combining NDT methods*. *Construction and Building Materials*, 33, 139–163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2011.12.103>

BS 1881: Part 204. (1988). *Testing concrete Part 204: Recommendations on the use of electromagnetic covermeters*. British Standards Institute. London, UK.

BS EN 302 066-1. (2019). *Short Range Devices (SRD); Ground- and Wall-Probing Radio determination (GPR/WPR) devices; Harmonised Standard for access to radio spectrum*. British Standards Institution. London, UK.

BS EN 12504-5. (2023). *Testing concrete in structures – Part 5: Determination of concrete cover using electromagnetic covermeters*. British Standards Institute.

Bungey, J., Millard, S. & Grantham, M. (2018). *Testing of concrete in structures*. 4th Edition. Taylor & Francis Group, Boston, FL.

Chang C-F. & Chen J-W. *The experimental investigation of concrete carbonation depth*. Cement and Concrete Research 2006;36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconres.2004.07.025>.

Chen, J., Jin, Q., Dong, B., & Dong, C. (2023). *Research on the Rebound Hammer Testing of High-Strength Concrete's Compressive Strength in the Xinjiang Region*. Buildings, 13(12). <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13122905>

Chen Y., Liu P. & Yu Z. (2018). *Effects of Environmental Factors on Concrete Carbonation Depth and Compressive Strength*. Materials, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma11112167>.

Devore J.L. (2015). *Probability and Statistics for Engineering and the Sciences*. 9th ed. Cengage Learning.

Donkervoort, J. (2024). *Reuse of concrete elements*. Master's Graduation Thesis. Eindhoven University of Technology, Eindhoven, the Netherlands. 204 p.

EC 1907/2006. (2006). *Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 December 2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH), establishing a European Chemical Agency, amending Directive 1999/45/EC and Repealing Council Regulation (EEC) No 793/93 and Commission Regulation (EC) No 1488/94 as well as Council Directive 76/769/EEC and Commission Directives 91/155/EEC, 93/67/EEC, 93/105/EC and 2000/21/EC*. Official Journal of the European Union, L 396/1. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2006/1907/oj>.

EN 12504-1. (2019). *Testing concrete in structures. Part 1: Cored specimens. Taking, examining and testing in compression*. European Committee for Standardization.

EN 12504-2. (2021). *Testing concrete in structures. Part 2: Non-destructive testing. Determination of rebound number*. European Committee for Standardization.

EN 12504-3. (2005). *Testing concrete in structures. Part 3: Determination of Pull-out Force*. European Committee for Standardization.

EN 12504-4. (2021). *Testing concrete in structures. Part 4: Determination of ultrasonic pulse velocity*. European Committee for Standardization.

EN 13791. (2019). *Assessment of in-situ compressive strength in structures and precast concrete components*. European Committee for Standardization.

EN 14629. (2007). *Products and systems for the protection and repair of concrete structures. Test methods. Determination of chloride content in hardened concrete*. European Committee for Standardization.

EN 1992-1-1. (2023). *Eurocode 2: Design of concrete structures – Part 1-1: General rules and rules for buildings, bridges and civil engineering structures*. European Committee for Standardization.

EN 206:2014. (2021). *Concrete. Specification, performance, production and conformity*. European Committee for Standardization.

EN ISO 15630-1. (2019). *Steel for the reinforcement and prestressing of concrete – Test methods – Part 1: Reinforcing bars, rods, and wire*. European Committee of Standardization.

EN ISO 6892-1. (2019). *Metallic materials – Tensile testing – Part 1: Method of test at room temperature*. European Committee of Standardization.

EU 2019/1021. (2019). *Regulation (EU) 2019/1021 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on persistent organic pollutants (recast)*. Official Journal of the European Union, L 169/45. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2019/1021/oj>.

fib Bulletin 111. (2024). *Modelling structural performance of existing concrete structures – State of the art report by the fib Task Group “Modeling of structural performance of existing concrete structures”*. fib, Lausanne.

Haavisto, J., Husso, A. & Laaksonen, A. (2020). *Compressive strength of core specimens drilled from concrete test cylinders*. *Structural Concrete*, 22: E683–E695. <https://doi.org/10.1002/suco.202000428>.

Haldar, A., & Mahadevan, S. (2000). *Probability, reliability and statistical methods in engineering design*. John Wiley & Sons, Inc.

Kiwa 73/07. (2017). *Eisen te stellen aan de interne kwaliteitsbewaking en het kwaliteitssysteem voor een kwaliteitsverklaring voor geprefabriceerde constructieve betonelementen [Requirements for internal quality control and the quality system for a quality statement for prefabricated constructive concrete elements]*. Kiwa Nederland B.V., Rijswijk.

Lahdensivu, J. & Tikkanen, J. (2025). *Tilaajan ohje: Uima-allastilojen betonirakenteiden kuntotutkimus*. [Customers guideline: Condition investigation of concrete structures in swimming pool spaces]. Concrete Association of Finland. 17 p.

Lahdensivu, J., Weijo, I., Ruuska-Jauhijärvi, K., Pyy, H. & Concrete Association of Finland. (2019). *Betonijulkisivun kuntotutkimus BY42* [Condition Investigation of Concrete Facades]. Concrete Association of Finland, 4th Edition. BY-Koulutus Oy, Helsinki.

Lai, W. W.-L., Dérobert, X., & Annan, P. (2018). A review of Ground Penetrating Radar application in civil engineering: A 30-year journey from Locating and Testing to Imaging and Diagnosis. *NDT and E International*, 96, 58–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ndteint.2017.04.002>.

Liu P., Yu Z. & Chen Y. (2020). *Carbonation depth model and carbonated acceleration rate of concrete under different environment*. *Cement and Concrete Composites* 2020;114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2020.103736>.

Liu M., Ju X., Wu L., Guo Q., Wang H. & Zhang W. (2023). *Carbonation depth model for loaded reinforced concrete (RC) beams under time-dependent relative humidity conditions*. *Journal of Building Engineering* 2023;65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2022.105618>.

Matthews, B., Allaix, D., Wijte, S., & Vullings, M. (2025a). *Advancing Non-Destructive Concrete Compressive Strength Estimation: Large-Scale Datasets and Machine Learning Framework* (unpublished manuscript).

Matthews, B., Allaix, D., Wijte, S., & Vullings, M. (2025b). *Non-destructive Estimation of Concrete Compressive Strength: Databases* [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14921019>.

Matthews, B., Allaix, D., Wijte, S., & Vullings, M. (2025c). *Non-destructive Methods for Reinforcement Mapping in Concrete Members: Databases* [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15003597>

Neville A. (2011) *Properties of Concrete*. 5th ed. Harlow: Pearson Education Limited.

NS 3682. (2022). *Hollow core slabs for reuse*. Standards Norway.

NT BUILD 381. (1991). *Concrete, Hardened: Air Void Structure and Air Content*. NORDTEST. Espoo, Finland.

Peng J., Tang H., Zhang J. & Cai S.C.S. (2018). *Numerical Simulation on Carbonation Depth of Concrete Structures considering Time- and Temperature-Dependent Carbonation Process*. *Advances in Materials Science and Engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/2326017>.

Pigeon, M. & Pleau, R. (1995). *Durability of Concrete in Cold Climates*. E & FN Spon. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781482271447>.

RT 103501. (2022). *Haitalliset aineet rakennuksissa. Tutkijan ohje. [Harmful substances in buildings. Guideline for investigator.]*. Rakennustieto.

Räsänen, A., Lahdensivu, J., Gudmundsson, K., Dervishaj, A., Westerlind, H., Lambrechts, T., Vullings, M., Arnold, V. & Huuhka, S. (2024a). *Properties and quality of precast concrete elements deconstructed in ReCreate's pilots*. The ReCreate project.

Räsänen, A., Lahdensivu, J., Vullings, M.W.F., Dervishaj, A. & Huuhka, S. (2024b). *Procedure for quality management of reclaimed concrete elements*. The ReCreate project.

Räsänen, A., Laaksonen, A. & Lahdensivu, J. (2025). *Sufficient number of core samples and method to determine compressive strength of in-use and reclaimed concrete elements*. *Structural Concrete*, <https://doi.org/10.1002/suco.70139>.

Räsänen, A. & Lahdensivu, J. (2025). *Sufficient sampling to determine the cover depth of reinforcement and carbonation depth for in-use and reclaimed concrete elements* (unpublished manuscript).

Selek, I. (2015). *Reliability of non-destructive testing methods for detecting steel rebar in existing concrete structures*. Master's thesis A-2015.113. Eindhoven University of Technology. <https://research.tue.nl/en/studentTheses/reliability-of-non-destructive-testing-methods-for-detecting-stee>.

SFS 4475. (1988). *Betoni. Pakkaskestävyys. Suojahuokossuhde. [Concrete. Freeze-thaw resistance. Protective pore ratio.]*. Finnish Standards Association SFS. Withdrawn.

SFS 5447. (1988). *Betoni. Säilyvyys. Jäädytys-sulatuskestävyys. [Concrete. Durability. Freeze-thaw resistance.]*. Finnish Standards Association SFS.

Tikkanen, J., Johansson, K., Kihula, J., Mantila, A., Punkki, J., Paukku, E., Ruuth, J. & Concrete Association of Finland. (2023). *Betoninormit 2021 BY65 [Concrete Codes 2021]*. Concrete Association of Finland, 6th Edition. BY-Koulutus Oy, Helsinki.

Tosti, F., & Ferrante, C. (2020). Using Ground Penetrating Radar Methods to Investigate Reinforced Concrete Structures. *Surveys in Geophysics*, 41(3), 485–530. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10712-019-09565-5>

TRGS 519. (2014). *Asbest. Abbruch-, Sanierungs- oder Instandhaltungsarbeiten*. Committee on Hazardous Substances AGS. Germany.

TRGS 521. (2008). *Abbruch-, Sanierungs- und Instandhaltungsarbeiten mit alter Mineralwolle*. Committee on Hazardous Substances AGS. Germany.

Tuutti K. (1982). *Corrosion of steel in concrete*. Stockholm: Swedish Cement and Concrete Research Institute.

Vullings M.W.F., Huuhka, S., Wijte S.N.M., Lambrechts, T., Houtman, J., Landman, M., Salmio, E., Räsänen, A., Jonker-Hoffrén, P., Weijo, I., Lahdensivu, J., Stenberg, E., Wedelsbäck, C., Appelqvist, T., Gudmundsson, K., Dervishaj, A., Westerlind, H., Hernandez Vargas, J., Henschel, C., Fischer, J. & Gottschling, D. (2024). *Best practice guidelines and recommendations for reuse-optimised deconstruction*. The ReCreate project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13828738>.

Wang J., Su H. & Du J. (2018). *Influence of coupled effects between flexural tensile stress and carbonation time on the carbonation depth of concrete*. Construction and Building Materials, 190. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2018.09.117>.

WHO. (2010). *WHO guidelines for indoor air quality: selected pollutants*. World Health Organization.

Wiwatrojanagul, P., Sahamitmongkol, R., & Tangtermsirikul, S. (2018). *A method to detect lap splice in reinforced concrete using a combination of covermeter and GPR*. Construction and Building Materials, 173, 481–494. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2018.04.027>

Zhou, F., Chen, Z., Liu, H., Cui, J., Spencer, B. F., & Fang, G. (2018). *Simultaneous estimation of rebar diameter and cover thickness by a GPR-EMI dual sensor*. Sensors (Switzerland), MDPI, 18(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/s18092969>